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Abstracts

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FunGlass

Application of the model of associated solutions to the study of the structure and properties of Li₂O-P₂O₅ glasses

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Abstract

Lithium phosphate glasses are important for their properties of ionic conduction, most particularly in the form of thin-films, when part of the oxygens are substituted by nitrogen, giving rise to the so-called LiPON solid electrolytes that have application in lithium batteries. The introduction of nitrogen in the phosphate composition improves their thermal and chemical properties and originates an increase of the ionic conductivity of the glasses, the last being explained through the decrease of the bridging to non-bridging oxygens ratio [1]. More recently, several authors have studied the structure and properties of phosphorus oxynitride phases with adequate values of conductivity and that may help in explaining the behavior of the LiPON electrolytes through their structural characteristics. In this work, we will show the first results on the application of the model of associated solutions, previously used by Shakhmatkin&Vedishcheva in glasses [2], for the study of the structure and properties of the Li₂O-P₂O₅ system. This will be useful for the analysis of the feasibility of its application in the prediction of the ionic conductivity of nitrogen containing phosphate electrolytes.

[1] N. Mascaraque et al., *Solid State Ionics* 233 (2013) 73.

[2] B.A. Shakhmatkin et al., *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 293 (2001) 220.